

TOPONYMY OF SOME CITIES OF THE FERGANA VALLEY

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Abstract: In this article, the history of the beautiful and charming Khoqandi Latif, types of handicrafts, their origin, The uniqueness of the Kokand craft school, especially wood carving will be detailed. You can also learn about the International Crafts Festival held in our city. Information about the holding of this festival, its purpose and the countries participating in the international festival will be given.

Key words: Fergana, city, Kokkan, village, Margilan, toponym, term, valley, appearance.

Fergana Valley, which is one of the regions with a unique position in our country, is rich in ancient and always famous cities. There are peculiarities in the topography of Ferghana Valley cities. In particular, Fergana, one of the largest cities of Uzbekistan, which is currently the center of Fergana region, was founded in 1877, and until 1907 it was called Yangi Margilan, and in 1907-1924 it was called Skoblev. The history of the toponymy of the Motherland is quite ancient, and it has traveled a long historical path under the name of Ferghana Valley. There are also legends about the toponym "Fergana". For example, according to legends, Ferghana was built by the Sasanian ruler Nushirvan (Anushirvan) and the king brought one tribe from each place to this place. Thus, people from different places built buildings and planted crops. People began to call them "Az har khana" - "those who come from different houses" (composite) because they came from different places. Then the suffix az was dropped and became Harkhana, which gradually took the form of Fergana. The same narration is given in "Kitab ul-masolik wal-mamolik" by Arab geographer Ibn Khurdadbeh (10th century), "Nuzhat ul-qulub" by Hamidullah Qazvini (1340) and other historical monuments¹. We can include the city of Margilan among the ancient cities of our country. It is especially noteworthy that the city of Margilan was brought to the attention of UNESCO and it was decided to celebrate its 2000th anniversary. Margilan is located in the southern part of the eastern half of the Fergana Valley. There is very little information about Margilan and its past history. When talking about the

¹ Qorayev S. Toponomika. – Toshkent, 2006. – B. 13 – 14.

toponymy of Margilan, Isaq Khan Ibrat's work "History of Fergana" is noteworthy. In this work, it is emphasized that the role of "poor peasant Bodyashins who came as immigrants from Persia and killed them" played a big role in the creation of the city of Margilan. The origin of the city's name is connected with the Persian word "murgu non", which means "chicken and bread". In the work "History of Ferghana" by Isaq Khan Ibrat, it is mentioned that the city of Margilon was founded at the request of these Persians, and it connects the founding of Margilon with Alexander the Great. It is said that during Alexander the Great's campaigns to the east, people from Persia who worked in Ferghana came to him with chicken and bread and asked him to build a city. Macedonians say "what is this?" they answered "Murgu non"². But we know from historical sources that Macedonian Alexander came to Khojand during his eastern campaigns. But he could not pass to the east of Ferghana. That is why Greek-Macedonian sources do not contain specific information about Fergana region. Only "behind Yaksart" was recorded the presence of some settled population³. Some people try to prove that Alexander came to Margilan with Alexander's tomb in Margilan. There is information about this cemetery in Ibrat's "History of Fergana": "...there is a shrine in Margilon named after King Iskandar, it is the place where he fell"⁴. But Fergana is considered as a territory that was not part of Alexander's kingdom. Our task is not to determine whether Alexander came to Margilon, but whether Margilon existed at that time. In the book "Historical Local History" by A. Nabiyeu, he cites the information of historians of the ancient world about Margilan. According to him, the Parthians were once a tribe expelled from among the Scythian tribes. The word "Parf" means "expelled people" in Scythian. Their clothes and languages are very close to each other. both the Parthians and the Margilians were skilled horsemen. They understood each other when they spoke. Based on this, the author suggests that the name "Fergana" was not Parfiyona - Parfona - Fergana. Sources indicate that the city of Margilan was founded in BC. Although the exact information about the city of Margilan has been written in written sources since the 10th century, we can say that the building period of this city is more than 2000 years based on the above evidence. Also, H. Khasanov in his work entitled "Explanation of Historical and Geographical Names" explains the word "Margylan" in the system of Mari, Margylan, Murg'ob toponyms, and the author of the book writes: "Murg'-ob" It can be interpreted as

² Ishoqxon Ibrat. Tarixi Farg'ona. – Toshkent, Kamalak, 1991. -B. 323 – 324

³ Xasanov H. O'rta Osiyo joy nomlari tarixidan. – Toshkent, 1965. -B. 54 – 55.

⁴ Ishoqxon Ibrat. Tarixi Farg'ona. – Toshkent, Kamalak, 1991. -B. 324

"double-water". Actually it is not. The basis of the names Murgab, Mari, as well as Margilan is derived from the ancient word "marg"⁵. There was also a Margi tribe in history. They lived in meadows and watery lands. Margzor means a forest, a green land, a meadow. The name Margilan has had many forms in history. For example: Marginon, Marginon, Murginon are among them. Toponymist E.M. According to Mirzayev, Margilan also had the form "Marginob". E.M. Mirzayev believes that the name Margylan is derived from the Tajik word "marg", meaning "meadow", and it is called Marg', Murg'ob, Marg'on, Marg'itta, Marg'ub. considered to be a peer. According to Suyun Karayev, the Marginan form of the name Marginon arose later as a result of Uzbek pronunciation. Near Samarkand there was also a toponym named Margilontepa. The word "marg" also means "spring" in the ancient Sogdian language. The word murgh, which has existed in the language of Tajik classical literature for a long time, means: grass, meadow, grass, meadow, i.e. meadow, meadow. Also, murgh also represented the name of the city of Murgab in that form. The words marg', margzor are found in the old Uzbek language, including in the works of Alisher Navoi: marg'-grass, a plant eaten by animals, margzor - meadow, a place where animals graze. In the "Dictionary of Navoi's works", one cannot agree with the designation of the words "marg" and "margzor" as Arabic. Connecting the toponyms Margilan and Marginon to the word marg-meadow has some dubious aspects. Because if that place was called Marg-otolak, weren't there other Marg-otolak around it? Also, if it is Marg'-ot, meadow, what do the components Marg'i-non, Marg'i-non, Marg'-inon-non in Marginon mean? If Bordi-yu, Margilan, Marginon, Marg are related to the name of the tribe, then it can be assumed that the second component of the toponym is related to the Persian-Tajik plural suffix-on (side). In this case, Marginon-Margiyon-Margin-Margin-Marginon-Margilan, i.e. the place where Margs live, probably means the city of Margs⁶. According to some legends, Margilon is said to be the tomb of Alexander the Great, and his flag is kept in the mosque. Until now, the name of one street is preserved as King Iskandar. Some people believe that the word "Margilan" comes from the name of Makedonsky (Alexander of Macedonia): Makedon-Macenon-Marginon-Margilan. In conclusion, it can be noted that the etymology of the toponym Margilan is currently unknown and requires additional scientific investigations.

⁵ Xasanov H. O'rtta Osiyo joy nomlari tarixidan. – Toshkent, 1965. -B. 54 – 55.

⁶ Xasanov H. O'rtta Osiyo joy nomlari tarixidan. – Toshkent, 1965. -B. 55.

One of the oldest cities of the Fergana Valley is the city of Kokan. Khoqandi Latif has developed as a place of culture and education since ancient times, the role of our ancient city in the development of our traditions and national values, inherited from our ancestors and polished to this day, is incomparable. There is also various information about the topography of the city of Kokan. In particular, the Kyrgyz epic "Manas" contains information about Tashkent, Samarkand, Jizzakh and the valley cities of Kokan, Andijan and Namangan, as well as their inhabitants and some types of economy. Also, the city of Koqan is mentioned in the manuscript "Hudud ul-Olam" written in the 10th century, in the works of Arab geographers Istahri, Ibn Havqal, and Muqaddasi in the forms Hoqan (Khuvaqand), Hoqand (Khuvaqand). Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur's work "Boburnoma" mentions Khokhan region. The current city of Kokand was founded in the beginning of the 18th century on the site of the historical Khokand by Shahrukhbiy, the head of the thousand clan of Uzbeks, the founder of the Kokand khanate. Academician V.V. According to Barthold, the correct form of the city from a literary point of view is Khoqand, which is the colloquial pronunciation of Koqand⁷.

Information about the city of Koqan is also found in the work of the Moroccan traveler Al-Idrisi "Nuzkhat af-mushtaq fi khtirak ul-afaq" ("Handful of one who is tired of wandering around the world"). The information about Khavaqand (Koqan) in "Mu'jam al-buldan" ("List of Countries"), a work of the 13th century traveler Yaqud Hamavi, is important for us. It is noteworthy that in the early sources it appears with names such as Kokan, Khavaqand, Khuvaqan, Khuvakent, Quqand. In turn, there are basically 3 hypotheses about the meaning of the term Kokan: 1. "Huk kand" means "pig dug" in Tajik. According to the sources, the reason for the emergence of such a view is that the place of the city was a reed field, where there were many wild pigs. 2. "Good" means "flattering". Because the city is located in a beautiful place. 3. "Good" and "latif" were used in relation to the city residents, and the verb "good" was used by the Kokan people. Also, "Khavokent" - "city of winds", "Kopkan" - "place of a lot of bloodshed", "Kopkan" - "ambush" and other names can be found in relation to the Kokan toponym. According to legends, the main reason why the city is called "Huk kand", which means "pig dug", is that before the city was built, these areas were swamps, because many pigs lived here. There are opinions that it is called The narration about this is given by Isaq Khan Ibrat in "History of Fergana"⁸. There is a

⁷ Bobobekov H. Qo'qon tarixi. Toshkent: Fan, 2006 - B. 5

⁸ Ishoqxon Ibrat. Tarixi Farg'ona. - Toshkent, Kamalak, 1991. - B. 285

legend that proves that the toponym of Kokand comes from the words "Khoqand" (pleasant, nice city, good city). When there was a need to build a city, experienced masters-city builders and experts in drawing up their plans advised their mayor to choose the most convenient place between the clean water and the stream. There were many gardens and parks in this place. The land itself was fertile. A natural barrier - two streams - protected the city from enemy invasion. In addition, caravan routes to China and other countries were connected in this area. All these are grounds for calling the city Khoqand⁹. According to another legend, the name of the city comes from the word "Havokent" (city of winds). Because, when the city was built, the residents note that the wind is frequent, and the trunks and trunks of trees are bent to one side under the influence of constant strong winds. That is why the city was called "Havokent" (in the sense of the city of winds, which often changes the air, cools the climate, opens the sea, and ensures its purity). According to another legend, the name of the city comes from the word "Kopkan" (a place where a lot of blood was shed). According to legend, in the distant past, when the city was built in this area, there were frequent wars. As a result of these wars, many people died and a lot of blood was shed. That is why the city is called "bloody". Later, the "P" was dropped in the pronunciation, and they began to call it "Kokon", and then, as a result of the change of "K" to "Q", they began to call it "Kokan". In another tradition, it is noted that the city was called "Kopkan" (trap, trap, ambush). In the past, foreigners often attacked the city to plunder and enslave its inhabitants. But all their efforts were in vain. In short, the invaders were ambushed and defeated. That is why the city is called "Kopkan", that is, a trap. Later, as a result of phonetic changes, "Kopqan" became "Koqan", "Koqand". Information about Kokan regions and cities, population and economy can also be found in the sources written during the Mongol, Timurid, Shaibani and Ashtarkhani periods. But this information is not complete.

REFERENCES:

1. Qorayev S. Toponomika.-Toshkent, 2006
2. Ishoqxon Ibrat. Tarixi Farg'ona.-Toshkent, Kamalak, 1991
3. Xasanov H. O'rta Osiyo joy nomlari tarixidan.-Toshkent, 1965
4. Bobobekov H.Qo'qon tarixi.-Toshkent:Sharq,1996
5. Bobobekov H.Qo'qon tarixi.-Toshkent:Fan ,2006

⁹ Bobobekov H.Qo'qon tarixi.Toshkent:Sharq,1996.-B. 10-12